

A NEW MODEL TO PREDICT THE ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF

A MISORIENTED SHORT FIBER COMPOSITE

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Summary

A percolation model combined with Monte Carlo method has been applied to two-dimensionally misoriented short fiber composites with the aim of predicting the effective electrical conductivity of the composite. Then, the threshold fiber length L_{th} was computed for several cases of misoriented short fiber composite, i.e., from completely random to reasonably well oriented short fiber composites. It was found in this study that the electrical conductivity of the composite increases drastically from the threshold fiber length and then approaches a constant value.

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1. Introduction

Polymers have been used as housing materials for electronics devices more widely than metals on account of various advantages, light weight, design flexibility and low cost. Rapid progress of office automations has produced the Electro-Magnetic Interference (EMI) problems resulting in a strong demand for electrically conductive housing materials (1-4). Thus, the housing for computer devices should be made of materials which have excellent EMI shielding properties. Electrically conductive materials have good EMI shielding capabilities. Polymer materials are basically insulator. Therefore, improvement of electrical conductivity of polymer materials is indispensable to use them as a material for computer housings.

Polymer-matrix composite (3-5) which contain conductive fibers as fillers are very promising, owing to their good mechanical properties. Electrical conductivity of such composites depends on several parameters, the volume fraction, aspect ratio and orientation angle distribution of conductive fibers. Some qualitative relations between these parameters have been reported (3), (5); however, the above relations are different from one case to another. Thus, there has been no unified theory to predict the electrical conductivity of a misoriented conductive short fiber composite except for spherical fillers (6). Gurland (6) studied the relationship between electrical resistivity and the volume fraction of conductive spherical particles. The curve of resistivity vs. volume fraction (f) of conductive spherical particles showed a critical value of f (f_c) beyond which the composite becomes conductive.

Percolation theory (7-9) has been used to describe electrical conduction in disordered materials. The conductivity of a composite with spherical particles can be predicted by the percolation theory. Unlike spherical fillers, there has been no attempt to predict the conductivity of a misoriented short fiber composite by use of a percolation theory.

In this study a percolation theory is applied to a composite composed of insulating matrix and conductive short fibers which are misoriented in a two-dimensional plane. Several percolation models for composites with spherical fillers will be reviewed first in section 2.1. Then a new model for a misoriented short fiber composite will be introduced in sections 2.2 and 2.3. The results will be shown and discussed in section 3. Then, the conclusion is given in section 4.

2. Fiber Percolation Model

2.1 Percolation Models

A percolation model (7-9) is composed of two simple elements, a site and a bond. A bond may connect a pair of sites, but that is governed by a stochastic mechanism. There are two types of mechanism. If the occupancy of bonds is governed by a stochastic mechanism, the problem is called "bond percolation problem," whereas if that of sites, the problem is called "site percolation problem." A path between two sites is said to exist if these two sites are connected by a sequence of sites and bonds. Charge may flow between two sites if the path between them exists. A set of occupied sites connected to one another through occupied bonds is called a cluster. The flow of charge may occur between any two sites in the same cluster, but no flow occurs between sites in different clusters unless the clusters are connected. When the probability (or the fraction) of occupied bonds or sites is small, then cluster size remains small and charge may flow only in the

local portion of a system. As the probability becomes larger, so do the clusters. When the probability reaches the critical value, the cluster size becomes infinite. At this stage, the system is said to be in a percolating state. The probability is translated as the volume fraction in practical problems, and its critical value is known as the critical volume fraction of conductive fillers.

2.2 Critical Fiber Length

The primary task in a percolation model is to find the critical probabilities in various systems. There are some exact solutions for regular lattice problems, but most of the solutions, particularly for random lattices, have been obtained by Monte Carlo experiment. To a regular lattice problem, a Monte Carlo Technique (8), (10), (11) can also be applied in such a way that bonds or sites of the regular lattice are removed at random lattice points with a given probability P . A composite with randomly scattered spherical particles can be considered as the regular lattice problems (6).

However, for a misoriented short fiber composite where the distribution of the fiber orientation angles is given by a proper function, a different Monte Carlo technique should be applied. Pike and Seager (12) developed a Monte Carlo technique for random-lattice percolation models. We will apply this technique to a misoriented short fiber composite and calculate the critical fiber length. For simplicity, only two-dimensionally misoriented short fiber composites will be considered in this paper.

We generate the coordinates (x,y) and orientation angle (θ) of each fiber by using pseudo-random number generator. Figure 1 illustrates this by focusing only on a short fiber in a unit cell which is considered as a composite. With a given uniform fiber length, we determine the end points of each fiber, then examine the connectedness of fibers. If two fibers have a contact point, they are said to be in the same cluster. However, the composite containing such clusters is not necessary in a percolating stage (see Figure 2(a)). A composite is said to be percolating if any two fibers on opposite boundary of the unit cell belong to the same cluster (see Figure 2(b)). A critical fiber length is defined as the minimum length that makes the composite percolating. After performing a reasonable number of tests, we calculate the average critical fiber length for several cases, i.e., combinations of number of fibers (N) and distribution $\rho(\theta)$ of fiber orientation angle θ .

2.3 Percolation and Electrical Conductivity

The electrical conductivity of a conductor-insulator mixture can be considered as a problem of random resistor network (13).

Then, the effective conductivity σ of the mixture can be expressed as

$$\sigma = \sigma_o (P - P_c)^t \quad (1)$$

where σ_o is the conductivity of a conductor, P is the probability of bonds or sites, P_c is the critical probability, and t is the critical exponent for the conductivity (14-17). To test the validity of the above equation, several experimental works (18-21) were conducted for the case of spherical conductor and a reasonably good agreement was obtained between eq. (1) and the experiments.

Figure 1. Definition of the coordinates, x and y , and the orientation angle θ of a short fiber in a unit cell.

Figure 2. (a) Locally connected state but not percolating and (b) percolating state of the same system with different fiber length for a completely random short fiber composite system. Only the fibers which form the percolating cluster at their critical length are shown in figures. The number of such fibers (N_f) is 322 out of $N=500$.

The objective of the present work is to obtain the relation between the electrical conductivity σ of a two-dimensionally misoriented short fiber composite and the length of short fibers. To this end we also use eq. (1), and probability (fraction) of bonds p in eq. (1) must be obtained from Monte Carlo experiment. However, the Monte Carlo method described in the previous section does not take any regular lattice as the base lattice, and hence does not yield any information about the extreme case, i.e., the case when $p = 1$. Thus, we employ a different approach to obtain p , which will be described below.

First, we make the following assumptions:

- (i) Fibers in the percolating cluster form the regular square lattice for the limiting case.
- (ii) The bond percolation criterion is used, and all the sites are given in the percolating cluster.

Assumption (i) is due to the fact that every intersecting point consists of just two fibers (see Figure 2), and the coordination number z of the base lattice is 4 where the coordination number is defined as the number of bonds emanating from a site. For example, the coordination number of the kagomé lattice is also 4. P_c depends on the type of base lattice, but can be represented by the following approximation (10),

$$zP_c = d/(d - 1) \quad (2)$$

where d is the dimensionality of the lattice. Eq. (2) gives us $P_c = 0.5$ for $z = 4$ and $d = 2$. Hence, P_c of the square lattice for the bond percolation problem is set equal to 0.5 (21). Assumption (ii) indicates that the sites of this percolation model consist of only the intersecting points and the fiber-end points. To see this more clearly, the case of six fibers is illustrated in Figure 3. In this figure we have $N_f = 6$, $N_i = 8$, $N_s = 20$, and $N_b = 22$, where N_f is the number of fibers, N_i is the number of intersecting points, N_s is the number of sites, and N_b is the number of bonds. There exist the following relations among these numbers.

$$N_s = 2N_f + N_i \quad (3)$$

$$N_b = N_f + 2N_i \quad (4)$$

The relation between N_s and N_b of the perfect square lattice is given by

$$N_{bo} = 2N_s \quad (5)$$

where N_{bo} is N_b of the extreme case, i.e., $p = 1$. From eqs. (3), (4) and (5), the probability of bonds can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} p &= N_b/N_{bo} = N_b/2N_s \\ &= (N_f + 2N_i)/(4N_f + 2N_i) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Thus, knowing N_f and N_i , we can calculate p by eq. (6). The critical

exponent t in eq. (1) depends also on the type of lattice. Lobb and Frank (22) have reported that $t = 1.35 \pm 0.02$ for the square lattice problem.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Critical Fiber Length

Although the critical fiber length calculated here is not a direct variable for obtaining the conductivity, it is a good index to see the effect of the orientation angle distribution on the conductivity. In our Monte Carlo experiments, short fibers are two-dimensionally misoriented in a unit square frame. It is assumed that the fiber orientation angle (θ) (see Figure 1) varies from $-\alpha$ to α (in degree) and $0 \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$ and its density $\rho(\theta)$ is uniform over $|\theta| \leq \alpha$ (see Figure 4). It is noted that for $\alpha = 90^\circ$, the composite is reduced to a completely random short fiber composite. The range of $15^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$ is focused on in this paper.

The total number of fibers N is an important factor because a percolation theory is based on the systems composed of an infinite number of elements. To see the effect of N , we have conducted two sets of experiments, namely, one for $N = 500$ and another for $N = 1000$. The experiments were done on an IBM 3081D. The number of samples (trials) for each condition is ten for $N = 500$, five for $N = 1000$. A calculation for $N = 1000$ takes an order of hours of CPU time even by this large computer. This is the reason why limited number of samples were calculated. The critical fiber length L_c was calculated as the average value over the values of ten samples and the results are shown in Table I. In spite of the limited number of samples, the standard deviation S of the critical fiber length L_c is reasonably small. The percolating cluster size N_f becomes smaller as α reduces. The layout of misoriented short fibers for $N_f = 500$ and $\alpha = 15^\circ$ is shown in Figure 5 where only the fibers in the percolating cluster are shown. A comparison between Figures 2(b) and 5 indicates that the smaller value of α yields narrower width (b) of the percolating cluster, i.e., $b = 0.755$ ($\alpha = 90^\circ$) and $b = 0.152$ ($\alpha = 15^\circ$).

Table I. The Results of the Monte Carlo Experiments

N	α	L_c	S	N_f
500	90	0.1083	0.0040	298
500	30	0.1300	0.0090	126
500	15	0.1628	0.0115	56
1000	90	0.0750	0.0026	474
1000	30	0.0950	0.0049	157
1000	15	0.1244	0.0029	109

N is the total number of fibers, α is the width of orientation angle distribution, L_c is the critical fiber length, S is the standard deviation of L_c , and N_f is the number of fibers in the percolating cluster.

Figure 3. An example of a percolating cluster composed of six fibers

Figure 4. Distribution of the orientation angles of the fibers in misoriented short fiber composite. The density $\rho(\theta)$ of orientation angle (θ) is uniform over $|\theta| < \alpha$.

Figure 5. Percolating cluster for reasonably well oriented short fiber composite. Only the 47 fibers in the percolating cluster out of $N=500$ are shown.

Figure 6. The orientation effect on the critical fiber length L_c .

To see this more clearly, we have plotted L_c as a function of α in Figure 6 for two cases of N , $N = 500$ and 1000 . L_c clearly becomes larger for more oriented composites (α becomes smaller). In the limiting case, L_c would be about unity as $\alpha \rightarrow 0$. This is because fibers have no width in our experiments and hence no possible contact in the fiber width direction occurs. The role of N can also be observed in Figure 6. For sufficiently large N , L_c should satisfy a rule of geometric similarity. That is, when N is doubled, the area containing doubled number of fibers should be twice as large as the original area. Therefore, L_c for $2N$ is related to L_c for N as

$$L_c(2N) = L_c(N)/\sqrt{2} \tag{7}$$

Since the values of L_c in Table I satisfy eq.(7), we can conclude that $N = 500$ is sufficiently large for percolation experiments.

3.2 Conductivity of the Composites

The results of the Monte Carlo experiments are shown in Table II for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ (completely random short fiber composite) and in Table III for $\alpha = 15^\circ$ (reasonably well oriented short fiber composite). In Table II the number of samples is ten for each case, P_p is an average value over ten samples, but the quantities N_f , p , b , σ_p are averaged among the samples which have percolating clusters, and σ is a geometric mean value of ten samples.

Table II.

L	P_p	N_f	p	b	σ_p	σ
0.09	0	-	-	-	-	10^{-15}
0.10	0.1	155	0.599	0.734	4.41×10^3	7.10×10^{-14}
0.11	0.8	374	0.619	0.951	5.69×10^3	9.59×10^{-1}
0.12	0.9	464	0.647	1.0	7.56×10^3	9.77×10^1
0.13	1	480	0.671	1.0	9.23×10^3	9.23×10^3
0.15	1	496	0.719	1.0	1.29×10^4	1.29×10^4
0.20	1	500	0.806	1.0	2.02×10^4	2.02×10^4

Properties of percolating cluster and conductivities for $N = 500$ and $\alpha = 90$, i.e., randomly oriented composites. L is the length of fibers, P_p is the probability of percolating clusters, N_f is the percolating cluster size, p is the probability of bonds defined by eq. (6), b is the width of a percolating cluster, σ_p is the conductivity of a percolating cluster defined by eq. (1) and σ is the effective conductivity of the composites (see also Figure 7).

Table III.

L	P_p	N_f	P	b	σ_p	σ
0.15	0	-	-	-	-	10^{-15}
0.16	0.2	47	0.571	0.165	2.82×10^3	3.39×10^{-12}
0.17	0.8	61	0.572	0.216	2.86×10^3	8.89×10^{-7}
0.18	1.8	72	0.578	0.261	3.25×10^3	1.25×10^3
0.20	2.6	119	0.606	0.342	1.84×10^3	4.37×10^3
0.25	1.4	344	0.667	0.744	8.97×10^3	9.41×10^3

Properties of percolating cluster and conductivities for $N = 500$ and $\alpha = 15^\circ$. All variables are defined in Table II. The results of σ are also shown in Figure 8.

For the case of completely random short fiber composite, the probability of percolating clusters P_D can be considered as the percolation probability because only one percolating cluster usually exists. On the other hand, for the case of reasonably well oriented short fiber composite (Table III) P_D can exceed unity, since more than one percolating cluster exist. In this case, P_D increases as L increases, but after passing the point $L = 0.2$, P_D begins to decrease. This is due to the coalescence of percolating clusters. As seen from Figure 5, the width of the percolating cluster b of reasonably well oriented short fiber composites remains narrow for small values of L , but it increases with L . The effective electrical conductivity σ of the composite may be given by

$$\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^m b_i \sigma_{pi} \quad (8)$$

where m is the number of percolating clusters, b_i and σ_{pi} is the width and conductivity of each percolating cluster, respectively. We have neglected in eq. (8) the conductivity of the matrix which can be considered as insulator. In order to calculate σ , we have used the following data on the conductivities of the constituents:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{matrix} & : \quad 10^{-5} \text{ Mho/cm} \\ \text{fibers} & : \quad 10^5 \text{ Mho/cm} \end{array}$$

Figures 7 and 8 show the results of $\log_{10} \sigma$ as a function of fiber length L for completely random and reasonably well oriented short fiber composites, respectively. It is seen from these figures that $\log_{10} \sigma$ increases drastically from a threshold value of L , then approaches a constant value (plateau). Let us define this threshold value (L_{th}) as the mid point of the steep slope of the $\log_{10} \sigma$ vs. L curve. Then L_{th} for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ and 15°

Figure 7. Logarithm of the effective electrical conductivity σ as a function of fiber length L for completely random short fiber composite.

Figure 8. Logarithm of the effective electrical conductivity σ as a function of fiber length L for reasonably well oriented short fiber composite.

are found as 0.105 and 0.170, respectively. The composite with $L \geq L_c$ can be considered as a conductive body. A step function type curve of $\log_{10} \sigma$ vs. f (volume fraction of fillers) similar to Figures 7 and 8 has also been observed for spherical fillers (6).

4. Conclusion

A percolation model was applied to a misoriented short fiber composite where the location of short fibers in a two-dimensional plane was created by Monte Carlo method. The fiber orientation varies from $-\alpha$ to α symmetrically with respect to the direction of electrical conduction. Then the conductivity of the composite was computed for various values of α . It was found that as α decreases, the width of the percolating cluster decreases, but the threshold value of fiber length beyond which the composite becomes conductive increases due to the assumption that all fibers are lines without breadth.

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